

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MALOTHA****FIRST NAME: EUNICE REFILOE****PROGRAM CODE: DILT****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 2%

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2016 on Windows 11 Pro)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Overview of academic essay writing (EUCLID 2021, 7 - 10)
2. Punctuation marks usage (EUCLID 2021, 16 - 23)
3. Dominant variants of world English (EUCLID 2021, 25 - 31)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 34 - 38)
5. Style guides (EUCLID 2021, 41 - 42)

ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

I have reviewed the ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack. Even though it is overwhelming, it is ultimately a very strategic learning tool. It is strategic in that it introduces one not only to the theory of academic writing but to the practical aspect, thereby equipping the scholar for the academic journey ahead.

Based on my review of the course pack, in this response paper, I discuss my understanding of the five concepts: an overview of academic essay writing, punctuation marks usage, dominant variants of world English, plagiarism, and style guides. Understanding these concepts is essential as it grounds one in the art of academic essay writing.

2) OVERVIEW OF ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

There are many types of essays. The focus of this discussion is on an academic essay. An academic essay aims to persuade readers of an idea based on empirical evidence (Cherry, n.d.). Such evidence should be sourced from credible authorities (EUCLID 2021, 7 - 8; UNSW Sydney n.d.). Therefore, scholars need instruction in academic writing to contribute meaningfully to the body of knowledge.

Basic steps guide academic essay writing (EUCLID 2021, 7). These steps include starting the process of writing sufficiently early, defining and analyzing the assignment, and then drafting an initial skeletal plan (EUCLID 2021, 7; UNSW Sydney, n.d.). These basic steps are helpful as they simplify the preliminary steps for scholars in writing an academic essay.

After initiating a skeletal plan based on one's understanding of the assignment, the next step is conducting thorough and relevant research (EUCLID 2021, 8). It is essential to engage with the research material through creative and critical thinking (EUCLID 2021, 9). After that, one should draft an essay plan and organize one's ideas (EUCLID 2021, 9; UNSW Sydney n. d). The research stage is critical as it enriches one's appreciation of the subject matter and informs the development of a thesis and answer.

After organizing one's ideas per the essay plan, the next step is to work on the first draft. This draft should include an introduction, body, and conclusion (EUCLID 2021, 10; UNSW, n.d.). It is advisable to edit and redraft the first draft several times before finalization and handover to ensure that one produces a properly cited, referenced, and well-balanced essay that explores ideas that support their submissions and contrary views (EUCLID 2021, 8-9). The ability to critically evaluate differing views, clearly articulating why one view is considered more compelling and ultimately weaving that into the conclusion, is essential for good academic essay writing (EUCLID 2021, 9).

3) PUNCTUATION MARKS USAGE

Punctuations are an integral part of academic writing. Therefore, as highlighted in the text, I will discuss various punctuation types and their usage. It is advisable to use minimal punctuation in a sentence while ensuring that the meaning of that sentence is not lost (EUCLID 2021, 16). I thought I was well conversant with all punctuation, but I found that while I knew all the punctuation marks in the text, I needed to learn about the formal names of some punctuations and how to use them in a text.

The punctuations I am conversant with include apostrophes, brackets, bullet points, colons and semicolons, commas, full stops, exclamation marks, and question marks. (EUCLID 2021, 16–22). An apostrophe denotes possession when used with a noun and an indefinite pronoun. It is also used in contractions, provided the two contracted words can be read separately before the contraction. Brackets can be round or square, among others.

The round brackets, like commas, are used within a sentence around a phrase that merely adds more information. Deleting the phrase in brackets should not distort the sentence.

The square brackets enclose edits by a subsequent person reviewing a document authored by a different person (EUCLID 2021, 17, 19). Given the above, I find that accurate usage of punctuation marks is crucial as they guide the reader through the ideas expressed in a sentence. Like road signs, punctuation marks can tell the reader when to slow down, speed up, and stop (University of Reading, n.d.).

Bullet points list items. Punctuations such as semicolons and full stops may be appropriate depending on the items listed. A colon heralds a concept inextricably related to the one before it. A semicolon links two parts of a sentence that are related. However, the two parts are independent because they can stand as complete and correct sentences (EUCLID 2021, 18). I find that punctuation marks break up sentences. In so doing, they contain and structure ideas, an essential attribute of academic writing. (University of Reading, n.d.).

A full stop, exclamation mark, and question mark are not to be simultaneously used at the end of a sentence. Instead, one at a time suffices. Quotation marks, double or single, enclose text directly quoted, such as titles, technical terms, and words or phrases that carry a subtext. (EUCLID 2021, 23; Montana State University, n.d.). Therefore, the discussion on the above punctuation marks is clear and practicable.

The punctuations that I knew but was unfamiliar with their formal names and usage in a sentence are the m-dash, the n-dash, and the ellipsis (EUCLID 2021, 20, 22). The m-dash is not to be used. However, the n-dash is usable in the same way that a comma and a round bracket work. While I know that an ellipsis indicates omitted text, I did not know the formal name of this type of punctuation. My overall assessment is that punctuation marks spice up academic writing and are indispensable. In their absence, academic writing would be lacking in structure.

4) DOMINANT VARIANTS OF WORLD ENGLISH

American and British English are dominant variants of World English (EUCLID 2021, 25). It is worth noting that, with the growth of American influence in the political and economic spheres, among others, since World War II, American English has had the most influence on World English (EUCLID 2021, 25). These two English variants are very similar, with subtle differences (EUCLID 2021, 25). For instance, while the spelling of words is the same, the pronunciation would be different (EUCLID 2021, 25). Conversely, while the spellings may differ, the pronunciations would be the same (EUCLID 2021, 25). Sometimes, the same concept but different terminology (EUCLID 2021, 26). Alternatively, the word may be the same but have a different or additional meaning (EUCLID 2021, 26).

The differences between these two dominant English variants are due to respective historical and cultural influences (EUCLID 2021, 25). The differences in these variants are not only limited to words but also extend to, among others, punctuations, such as periods,

commas, and quotation marks, as well as the writing of dates (EUCLID 2021, 31). The most important thing to do in academic writing is to choose one variant and be consistent.

5) PLAGIARISM

According to Merriam-Webster's online dictionary (2023), plagiarism is stealing and passing off ideas or words of another as one's own or using another's production without crediting the source. One should, therefore, desist from committing plagiarism as it is wrong, unethical, unfair, and a serious academic offense with severe consequences (EUCLID 2021, 34). Crediting authorities by citing their work eliminates plagiarism from one's work. There are two ways to cite: in text and listing the works cited (EUCLID 2021, 34). Therefore, I find proper citation of the source of information critical as it is the only way to avoid plagiarism.

In-text citation entails referencing the original work within the text instead of inserting a footnote. (EUCLID 2021, 35). Such original work is distinguishable through quotation marks (EUCLID 2021, 35). Short quotations are put in quotation marks, while long quotations, usually over four lines, require indentation and look like separate miniature paragraphs without quotation marks (EUCLID 2021, 35). Excessive use of quotation marks defeats originality of thought in academic writing. Therefore, it is advisable to use quotation marks sparingly and only when necessary for one to make their point (EUCLID 2021, 37).

Paraphrasing is another form of in-text citation. It entails expressing the same idea as the originator of the work but using one's own words and style (EUCLID 2021, 36). When paraphrasing, it is imperative not to distort the meaning intended by the original writing.

As mentioned above, citations can also be through a list of works cited. These are references that appear in a list format at the end of a written work. The list of works cited is an extension of in-text citations as it provides publication information relating to in-text citations (EUCLID 2021, 38). The two mutually coexist and should be utilized to avoid intellectual property theft of written works.

6) STYLE GUIDES

Prescribed rules that ensure that a writer's work looks and reads just like every other work written in that style that is, the look of the page, the citation of other authors in the body of the work, and even the tone of the writing; are known as style guides. (Purdue University, n.d.). Style guides ensure consistency in the presentation of work written in a particular style and are an invaluable tool for any writer (EUCLID 2021, 41-42).

Style guides are different and unique to various disciplines. For instance, there are style guides on technical writing, business or commercial writing, journalism, web

copywriting, and so on (EUCLID 2021, 41). Therefore, style guides are a form of branding unique to different disciplines (Purdue University, n.d.).

Guidelines for a particular writing style are published and thus accessible by writers. Thus, different publishing houses have style guides that are associated with them (EUCLID 2021, 41). Writers, therefore, have the benefit of choosing a particular style of writing that aligns with that of the publishing house they will eventually publish their work with.

I am particularly impressed by the predictability a style guide affords many writers in their varied disciplines (EUCLID 2021, 41). I am excited to present my Response Paper 1, following the Chicago Rules (Turabian), as it will be my first time following a particular style guide. At the same time, I am nervous about whether or not I am following the guidelines properly.

7) CONCLUSION

Academic writing requires one to have an understanding of certain basic concepts. In view thereof, the above discussion provides an overview of academic essay writing. It also highlights popular punctuation marks and their usage. Further, it examines dominant variants of world English, focusing on their similarities and differences. Additionally, it underscores the importance of avoiding plagiarism. Finally, it explores the concept of style guides and their importance. Therefore, understanding the highlighted concepts is critical in grounding a scholar in the art of academic writing.

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